

On the Nature of the Time-Dilution Curves in Some Hemolytic Systems.

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In three previous papers (Sen and Basu, *Ind. Jour Med. Research*, 1928, **15**, 581 ; This *Journal*, 1928, **5**, 1 ; Sen and Sen, This *Journal*, 1928, **5**, 261) we have studied certain aspects of hemolysis in presence of serum. While thus studying the hemolysis by bile salts, we were confronted with certain results of a very peculiar type in the time-dilution curves of some of these hemolytes which required further investigation. The present paper is a continuation of our previous studies, and contains results of some determinations of time-dilution curves with several hemolytic substances. Many determinations of these time-dilution curves with different hemolytes and blood corpuscles have been made from time to time, and among these we can mention the works of MacLean and Hutchinson (*Biochem. J.*, 1909, **4**, 369) and Ponder (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1922, **93B**, 86 ; 1923, **95B**, 42 ; 1926, **99B**, 465 ; 1927, **101B**, 205). Our interest in this subject was aroused by some observations of MacLean and Hutchinson. These authors studied the hemolysis of sheep corpuscles by the sodium salts of glycocholic and choleic acids and came to the conclusion that these substances are capable of producing hemolysis in the ordinary way when strong doses are used, but exhibit marked peculiarities when present in considerably weaker amounts. It was found that under similar conditions the same hemolytic effect can be produced in a given time by widely divergent amounts of the salts. Between these two points lies what may be termed a more or less neutral zone, in which the hemolysis is very considerably delayed depending on the relative amounts of the hemolytic agent employed. Ponder in recent times has confirmed this result with glycocholate, but according to him sodium taurocholate does not give any peculiar result of this sort, and the time-dilution curve is of a much simpler nature. In view of the fact that taurocholic acid is closely related to the other acids

studied by MacLean and Hutchinson, it is surprising that the salt of this acid would behave in an entirely different manner. Also, since no explanation of the so-called "hemolytic paradox" was offered by MacLean and Hutchinson, it seemed desirable to study the subject anew in order to find out a suitable explanation for the peculiarities observed. Some time-dilution curves have therefore been obtained with different hemolytes, and this paper contains part of the results.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The method of experimentation is in principle the same as given in the previous papers. Since the determination of the end-point is a colourimetric one, particular care was taken to select glass tubes of equal transparency, the bore and the thickness being the same. The mixing of the corpuscle with the hemolyte was finished within 10 seconds, and the tube was then allowed to stand in a uniform temperature, and generally was not at all disturbed except in those cases where the time necessary for complete hemolysis was very high. An interesting fact in connection with the hemolysis by some hemolytes used in this paper is that when the hemolyte and the corpuscles are mixed together as soon as hemolysis starts, the reaction appears to be very rapid and in many cases near about 90% of the cells are hemolysed within a comparatively short period. The first stage in hemolysis thus seems to be of the nature of an autocatalytic reaction. The remaining amounts of the corpuscles however take an appreciable amount of time for hemolysis, and there appears to be a retardation when the last stage in complete hemolysis is reached. When observed visually, the last trace of turbidity of the corpuscle and hemolyte mixture takes a fairly long time to disappear completely unless the hemolyte is in great excess.

The experiments given in the present paper were all done with sheep's erythrocytes. Defibrinated corpuscles were repeatedly washed by normal saline in order to free them from serum, and were then suspended in normal saline to give a concentration of 5 per cent. In the actual experiments, 1 c.c. of this cell suspension was used in every case unless otherwise mentioned. The total volume of the suspension *plus* hemolyte was always made up to 5 c.c. by the previous addition of normal saline if

necessary. Among the hemolytes used, potassium oleate and saponin were obtained from Kahlbaum, sodium taurocholate from Merck, and the solutions were freshly prepared to prevent any change in the nature of these substances in solution on standing. Special care was taken with the taurocholate which was prepared only 10 minutes before the actual experiment was carried out. The taurocholate concentration was 3 per cent, and it may be stated that the concentration of the hemolyte is almost the same as used by MacLean and Hutchinson with choleate and glycocholate, the corpuscles being in both cases of sheep of identical concentration. The concentration of taurocholate used by Ponder was however low. All the hemolytes were dissolved in normal saline. Two different samples of sheep corpuscles have been used, and for one experiment a slightly hemolysed sample of erythrocyte suspension was taken. The temperature was 32°, and the corpuscles, when not in use, were kept in an ice-chest, the temperature being always below 5°.

The first table contains the results of oleate hemolysis. A stock solution of one per cent potassium oleate was prepared and from this a 1 in 10,000 oleate was prepared.

TABLE I.

Oleate in c.c.	Final conc.	Time of complete hemolysis in minutes,	Remarks.
0.5	1/100,000	>130	} No hemolysis in these times.
0.8	1/62,000	>130	
1.0	1/50,000	115	
1.2	1/41,000	72	
1.5	1/33,330	35	
1.8	1/27,770	18	
2.0	1/25,000	10	
2.5	1/20,000	5	
3.0	1/16,660	2	

In Table II are given a few data with different amount of corpuscles. Oleate concentration has been 2 c.c. of 1 in 10,000.

TABLE II.

Amount of cells in c.c.	1.0	1.5	2.0
Time for complete hemolysis in minutes	10	30	100

In Table III are given the data on taurocholate hemolysis. The peculiar time periods are to be noted.

TABLE III.

Taurocholate in c.c.	Final conc.	Time for hemolysis in minutes.
0.1	1/1666	26
0.5	1/333	8
1.	1/166	16
1.5	1/111	11
2.0	1/83.3	27½
2.5	1/66.6	42
3.0	1/55.6	27
3.5	1/47.6	5

In Table IV are given some data of alkali hemolysis. Caustic soda N/10 was prepared in normal saline.

TABLE IV.

NaOH in c.c.	Final conc.	Time for hemolysis in minutes.	Remarks.
0.1	N/500	> 135	Only slight hemolysis.
0.3	N/166.6	66	
0.5	N/100	31	
0.7	N/71.4	19	
1.0	N/50	12	
1.3	N/38.5	9	
1.5	N/33.3	7½	
2.0	N/25	4½	

In Table V are given some data on acid hemolysis. Hydrochloric acid N/50 was prepared in saline and this solution was used in the experiments.

TABLE V.

HCl in c.c.	Final conc.	Time for hemolysis in minutes.	Remarks.
0.1	N/2500	> 45	No hemolysis.
0.2	N/1250	45	About 40 per cent. hemolysis in this time
0.4	N/625	25	
0.6	N/416.6	14	
0.8	N/312.5	9	
1.0	N/250	6	

In studying this acid hemolysis, it was observed that not only hemolysis took place but along with it the hemoglobin turned brown and finally a sedimentation was formed. In order to determine the correct end-point in these cases, a simultaneous count of the R.B.C. was made under the microscope. It was observed that when the end-point in hemolysis was reached, there was practically no R.B.C. in the microscopic field, but even one or two minutes before the time of complete hemolysis, large number of R.B.C. were to be observed under the microscope.

In Table VI some data are given of the effect of alkali on oleate hemolysis. The object was to find out if there was any retardation of hemolysis. Several previous authors have found out this (Ponder, *loc. cit.*), but when actually doing the experiments, some peculiar results have been obtained which, it seems, have not been observed by any one before. The corpuscles were slightly hemolysed and hence a fresh determination of the time-dilution curve with pure oleate was also made. The concentration of oleate was 1 in 10,000.

TABLE VI.

Oleate pure c.c.	Time of hemolysis.	Oleate + 0.1c.c. N/10 NaOH.	Time of hemolysis.
1.0	100	1.0	45
1.2	68	1.2	36
1.5	34	1.5	24
1.8	14	1.8	28
2.0	11	2.0	22
2.2	9	2.2	19

The data given in Table VI are interesting. When the concentration of oleate is low, alkali accelerates the hemolysis, but when the oleate concentration is high, alkali retards the hemolytic effect of oleate. When observation is made on the actual progress of hemolysis in the tubes, a curious thing is observed. With the same concentrations of oleate, hemolysis always starts first in those tubes which contain alkali, but when oleate concentration is comparatively higher, pure oleate hemolysis ultimately gets faster than hemolysis by the mixture of oleate and alkali. With lower concentrations of oleate however mixed hemolytes have a better action. In view of this surprising fact, it was decided to repeat the experiment with a fresh sample of corpuscles because the earlier sample had become a little aged, and a few corpuscles were already laked. In Table VII these results are given. The oleate was freshly prepared, and the corpuscle concentration was the same as before. The concentration of oleate was 1 in 10,000.

TABLE VII.

Oleate pure c.c.	Time for hemo- lysis.	Oleate + 0.1 c.c. N/10 NaOH.	Time for hemo- lysis.
1.0	> 120	1.0	74
1.2	62	1.2	55
1.5	27	1.5	41
1.8	12	1.8	36
2.0	9	2.0	27
2.5	7	—	—

A perusal of the data given in Table VII will immediately show that these results entirely confirm those given in Table VI. Consequently we have to resume that the phenomenon is true and hence an explanation has to be found for these interesting, though apparently abnormal, effects of alkali in oleate hemolysis.

Since we have found certain abnormalities in oleate and taurocholate hemolysis, it was now thought desirable to investigate more fully the case of saponin hemolysis which, according to several

authors, does not show any abnormality. In Table VIII the results are given. The saponin concentration as given below is 1 in 10,000, but in actual experimentation, sometimes a 1 in 1,000 solution has been used. The solutions were prepared from a stock solution of 1 in 100 which was also freshly prepared.

TABLE VIII.

Saponin.	Final conc.	Time of hemolysis.	Remarks.
0.5	1/100,000	> 5½ hours	No hemolysis at all.
1.0	1/50,000	> 5½ hours	About 10% hemolysis.
1.5	1/33,333	> 5½ hours	About 20% hemolysis.
2.0	1/25,000	> 5½ hours	About 40% hemolysis.
2.5	1/20,000	> 5½ hours	About 60% hemolysis.
3.0	1/16,666	> 5½ hours	About 80% hemolysis.
3.5	1/14,286'	258	
4.0	1/12,500	230	
4.5	1/11,111	71	
5.0	1/10,000	50	
5.5	1/9090	43	
6.0	1/8333	35	
6.5	1/7692	30	
8.0	1/6250	16	
10.0	1/5000	10	
12.0	1/4166	4	
15.0	1/3883	3	
20.0	1/2500	1½	

In Table IX the effect of alkali on saponin hemolysis is shown

TABLE IX.

Saponin + 0.1 c.c. N/10-NaOH.	Time of hemo- lysis.	Saponin pure c.c.	Time of hemo- lysis.
5.0	156	5.0	50
8.0	73	8.0	12
10.0	56	10.0	10
12.0	50	12.0	4
15.0	21	15.0	3

The results in Table VIII show that no abnormality is observed in the saponin series, and Table IX shows that alkali has always a retarding influence and the series is therefore unlike that of oleate. For this reason it was thought desirable to repeat our previous work on taurocholate hemolysis with this new sample of corpuscles. The taurocholate solution was freshly prepared and was 3 per cent. strong. The data in Table X show the results. For comparative purposes, the effect of alkali is also shown in this table.

TABLE X.

Taurocholate in c c	Time of hemo- lysis.	Taurocholate + 0.1 c c NaOH.	Time
0.1	14	0.1	} No hemolysis in any of the tubes in 35 minutes. Complete inhibition within this period.
0.5	2	0.5	
1.0	10	1.0	
1.5	10½	1.5	
2.0	14	2.0	
2.5	14½		
3.0	10½		
3.5	4		

The results of Table X thus entirely confirm those given in Table III.

Discussion.

The results presented in the previous pages may be discussed primarily from two points of view, namely whether the time-dilution curves with different hemolytes are normal or abnormal, and secondly whether the effect of alkali is the same in all the cases. In Fig.

I the time dilution curves of the different hemolytes are plotted in

FIG. I.

the same paper which would thus give a comparative representation of the nature of the curves. For obvious reasons, the time and concentrations cannot be plotted according to the same scale with different hemolytes, and so these curves do not show the efficiency of these hemolyzers on sheep's corpuscles. Also saponin is included in these curves though the experiments were made with a different sample of cells. The point of interest in these curves is that no abnormality is to be noticed in the case of hemolytes saponin, caustic soda, potassium oleate and hydrochloric acid, but there is a marked peculiarity when sodium taurocholate is used. This agrees with the type of results obtained by MacLean and Hutchinson, but

does not agree with those obtained by Ponder or Yeager (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1928, 11, 77 θ). According to our results sodium taurocholate hemolysis is quite analogous to the glycocholate hemolysis. It is not possible to state definitely why Ponder's results are different, but a suggestion may be made that Ponder's experiments were carried out with much lower concentrations of the hemolyte and corpuscles and this may have an important bearing on the nature of the time-dilution curve of sodium taurocholate. Similarly if we look at the other end of the series, namely with higher concentrations of the taurocholate, it will be apparent from a study of the results given in Tables III and X, that when the taurocholate concentration exceeds 2.5 c. c. per 5 c. c. of the mixture, the fall in the amounts of time necessary for complete hemolysis is regular and there appears to be no abnormality. Hence if experiments are carried out only within this range of hemolyte concentration, a normal time-dilution curve can be obtained. We believe that with very low concentrations of the taurocholate, a similar normal time-dilution curve is to be expected. Our experimental observation will also explain another fact. Ponder found that glycocholate is a very weak hemolyte as compared to taurocholate, but we have found previously (Sen and Basu, *loc. cit.*) that glycocholate is a much stronger hemolyte than taurocholate. This difference probably depends upon the fact that we have been comparing the two hemolytes in concentrations far different from that used by Ponder. It is quite possible that in the concentrations we had been using, the comparison has been made in that portion of the curves where the action of taurocholate was about the minimum but the effect of glycocholate was near about the maximum. This would show that glycocholate is the stronger hemolytic agent. In the experiments of Ponder however the concentrations of the comparing hemolytes may have been such that the conditions are just the reverse of that of ours, and hence an entirely different result was obtained. The problem of hemolysis by the salts of the complex bile acids is so complicated that it appears that divergent results are only to be expected at present till a more thorough investigation is made. Thus our experience with glycocholate hemolysis leads us to the belief that this particular hemolysis which is known to give an abnormal series and shows the so-called "hemolytic paradox" of MacLean and Hutchinson can be made to give a normal time-dilution curve if a suitable and comparatively high concentration range is chosen. This view is also strengthened by a perusal

of the actual results obtained by MacLean and Hutchinson with sodium cholalate, choleate and glycocholate. It is observed from their data that with sodium cholalate, the time-dilution curve up to a concentration of 0.1 c.c. of M/10-cholalate in a 5 c.c. mixture gives a normal series. Again from a concentration of 0.8 c.c. up to 3 c.c. of the cholalate, the time-dilution curve is perfectly normal. The abnormality is only to be noticed between the concentration range 0.1 and 0.8 c.c. Similarly with sodium choleate, the time-dilution curve is normal up to a concentration of 0.1 c.c. M/10 of the salt and then again between the range 1.0 and 3.0 c.c. but is abnormal between the range 0.1 and 1.0 c.c. of the hemolyte. With sodium glycocholate the curve is normal up to 0.08 c.c. and then again from 0.5 to 3.0 c.c. These results therefore support our conclusion arrived experimentally that an abnormality in taurocholate hemolysis can be expected and that the difference in our results from that of some other workers is to be attributed to different experimental conditions. The assumption that we may expect a normal series in the time-dilution curve of taurocholate when the concentration of the hemolyte is low has also been experimentally confirmed by us and the results are given in Table XI. In order to use a low concentration of the hemolyte, we were obliged to use a low concentration of the cells. In the following table, 1 c.c. of an one per cent suspension prepared by diluting the previously used corpuscles in saline has been used. The taurocholate concentration is 0.3 per cent. The cell suspension is the same as used in Tables VIII to X. In the final mixture the concentration of the cells is 1/5th of that used in other tables.

TABLE XI.

Taurocholate in c.c.	Final conc.	Time of hemolysis in minutes.
0.1	1/16666	>2 hours
0.2	1/8333	>2 hours
0.3	1/5555	24
0.4	1/4166	7
0.5	1/3333	4
0.6	1/2777	3 mins. and 15 secs.
0.7	1/2381	2 mins. and 30 "
0.8	1/2083	1 min. and 30 "
0.9	1/1851	1 min. and 7 "
1.0	1/1666	0 min. and 55 "
1.2	1/1389	0 min. and 40 "

From this table and from Fig. II it will be immediately observed

FIG. II.

Time-dilution curve of sodium taurocholate in low concentrations with small amount of erythrocytes.

that there is no abnormality in the time-dilution curve within the particular concentration range of the hemolyte and the cell suspension. Thus the result of some investigators who have found a normal series with taurocholate is confirmed for a particular experimental condition. But taking the complete data of taurocholate hemolysis into consideration, we come to the conclusion that sodium taurocholate also may show the "hemolytic paradox" and in this respect is quite analogous to other salts of the bile acids. So far as other hemolytes studied in this paper are concerned, all of them appear to be normal, but some more experiments are being tried with the oleate.

The second interesting point is that of the effect of alkali on the hemolytic systems. In an earlier paper (Sen and Basu) it was shown that for some concentrations of OH ions, an inhibitory effect on hemolysis is to be expected, which is found to be a fact so far as saponin or taurocholate hemolysis is concerned. With oleate however, the peculiar result has been obtained that alkali acts as a

retarder of hemolysis when higher concentrations of oleate are used, but acts as an accelerator when comparatively lower amounts of oleate are used. We are at present unable to give an explanation of this behaviour, and the existence of the hemolytic paradox remains also unexplained, but we are continuing our experiments in these lines.

Summary.

(1) Time-dilution curves of hemolysis have been obtained with hydrochloric acid, caustic soda, saponin, potassium oleate and sodium taurocholate and sheep's erythrocytes.

(2) It is found that taurocholate gives an abnormal time-dilution curve, but other hemolytes show a normal series within the particular concentration range studied.

(3) It is shown that the so-called hemolytic paradox can be observed with taurocholate also when the concentration range of the hemolyte used is fairly wide. It is pointed out that the variation in the nature of the results of taurocholate hemolysis found in this paper from that of some other workers is probably due to the fact they have used a lower concentration of the hemolyte and corpuscles. Incidentally it has been emphasised that the actual concentrations used in the hemolytic systems may greatly influence the nature of the time-dilution curves.

(4) It has been observed in oleate hemolysis that the effect of small amount of alkali is twofold. At lower concentrations of oleate, alkali has an accelerating effect on hemolysis, but with higher concentrations of oleate, an inhibitory action is observed. The amount of alkali is however such that no visible action is noticeable when it is present alone within the experimental period.

(5) With saponin or taurocholate, alkali has a uniform retarding action. This confirms the result of previous workers and is in line with the mechanism of hemolysis discussed in a previous paper.

(6) Sodium glycocholate may have either a greater or lower hemolytic action than sodium taurocholate depending on the particular concentration range of the salts and the corpuscle concentration in which the comparison is made.

